

How Open Data is Reshaping Development Practices in Nigeria

Mohammed, Muideen Olakunle

A dissertation submitted to the School of International Development of the University of East Anglia in Part-fulfilment of the requirements for the Degree of Master of Arts in International Development

September 2023

Word Count: 11,973

Acknowledgment

I am infinitely grateful to Allah (S.W.T), to Robert Grant, my lecturers, UEA and my wife, Yetunde.

SUMMARY

Although extensive research has been conducted on open data's impact on development. The studies corroborate that open government data (OGD) has brought about positive transformations across all dimensions of development. Meanwhile, far less exploration has occurred on OGD influence on development practices in Nigeria. This study set out to investigate OGD portals' impact on transparency, accountability, and good governance within the Nigerian context. It achieves this through comprehensive analysis of government websites and portals, and interviewing key stakeholders using OGD for advocacy.

The findings of this study affirm that OGD portals, including NOCOPO, open treasury portal, NBS, and BOF website, have significantly enhanced transparency by providing unprecedented access to government expenditure, procurement activities, and budget performance. This transparency has led to the emergence of data-driven advocacy campaigns by Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), which hold public officials accountable and empower local communities in demanding transparency.

However, challenges persist in data accessibility, completeness, and delays in publication. This study makes a case for establishing a centralized data repository, fostering collaboration between government institutions and CSOs, and ensuring continuous data collection to support equitable policy decisions.

Keywords: open data Nigeria, open government data Nigeria, NOCOPO, BudgIT, CODE, Ominira

CONTENTS

Acknowledgement.....	iii
SUMMARY.....	iv
1.0 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1 Research background.....	1
1.2 Problem statement.....	3
1.3 Research purpose.....	3
1.4 Research objectives.....	3
1.5 Research questions.....	4
1.6 Research structure.....	4
1.7 Contributions to knowledge.....	4
2.0 REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND KEY CONCEPTUAL IDEAS.....	6
2.1 The concept of open data.....	6
2.2 The concept of transparency.....	7
2.3 Open data and Transparency.....	8
2.4 The role of open data in development practices.....	9
2.5 Open data and Accountability.....	11
2.6 Fiscal transparency and good governance.....	11
2.7 Open data and good governance.....	13
2.8 Summary of reviewed literature.....	14
3.0 DESCRIPTION OF METHODS AND SAMPLING.....	16
3.1 Study approach.....	16
3.2 Sampling technique.....	17
3.3 Data collection.....	17
3.4 Data analysis.....	18
4.0 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION.....	19
4.1 OGD portals.....	19
4.2 Thematisation of participant positions.....	30
4.2.1 Data accessibility.....	33
4.2.2 Data availability.....	33
4.2.3 Data monitoring.....	33
4.2.4 Data visualization.....	35
4.2.5 Data protection and privacy.....	35

4.2.6	Data quality.....	36
4.2.7	Data use.....	37
4.2.8	Missing data.....	37
4.2.9	FOI.....	38
4.2.10	Open data challenges.....	39
4.3	Summary of findings.....	39
4.4	Limitations of the research.....	40
4.5	Implications for policy.....	41
5.0	CONCLUSION	42
5.1	Recommendations.....	43
5.2	Inferences and further study.....	43
	Bibliography	45
	Appendix 1.....	53
	Appendix 2.....	54

1.0 INTRODUCTION

In these digital times, data has become a significant lifeblood for deciding, measuring, and facilitating policies. More importantly, to track and guide development progress, data has become a powerful tool. The collection, analysis and interpretation of data have become essential practices across the globe.

From the viewpoint of open data initiatives which seek to ensure that government-held data is accessible to the public, this initiative has emphasized how data is instrumental for impacting governance, transparency, accountability, innovation, and economic growth. This is due partly to how availability and transparency of government data has the potential to reshape governance practices, enhance citizen engagement, and foster socio-economic advancement. This dissertation seeks to analyze open data initiatives impact within Nigeria and its influence on governance, accountability, and transparency from various perspectives.

1.1 Research background

In recent years, the development landscape across nations has witnessed a paradigm shift towards open data as an accelerator for positive societal changes. The current digital revolution has intensified demand for transparency and accountability and laid the foundation for the flourishing of open data initiatives. These initiatives involve the disclosure of various government datasets such as budgetary allocations, public procurement process, healthcare statistics and social statistics, and enabling citizens and stakeholders to access and utilize this information for informed decision-making and to scrutinize and hold government accountable at every turn (World Bank, 2015).

Providing public access to government data advertently empowers citizens and CSOs to monitor government actions, detect inefficiencies and demand greater accountability from their governments and leaders (Saxena and Muhammad, 2018; United Nations Development Programme, UNDP 2022). The introduction of OGD platforms in low- and high-income countries shows how governments attempt to promote accountability and combat corrupt practices (Iwasaki and Obi, 2015).

The game-changing capability of open data is particularly relevant in the context of Nigeria, a nation grappling with diverse socio-economic challenges and a need for inclusive governance, transparency, and accountability. Issues such as corruption, unequal

resource distribution, and limited citizen engagement have underscored development practices. However, open data initiatives present a potential avenue to address these challenges by providing citizens with the tools to monitor government activities, demand accountability, and participate in decision-making.

This potential is further accentuated by Nigeria's expanding digital infrastructure and increasing internet penetration. In recognition of open data's potential to foster good governance, the Nigerian government took steps towards implementation of an OGD. The federal government joined the Open Government Partnership (OGP)¹ in 2016, afterwards it launched several data portal for ministries and agencies to publish data and budget allocation. Also, the establishment of some state data portals² shows the commitment of government to data-driven governance.

The momentum towards open data adoption by the government and its agencies is widely commended. However, this dissertation will endeavour to address the following inquiries: How effectively have these portals improved the accessibility and availability of government data to the citizens? To what extent do they genuinely promote fiscal transparency and accountability? How do they influence institutional transparency outcomes? And equally important, what barriers impede the seamless integration of open data into governance practices in Nigeria?

Addressing these questions requires a comprehensive examination of the multi-dimensional features of open data initiatives in Nigeria. By analyzing the viewpoints of researchers, policy makers, civil society organizations, and public data users, this research seeks to contribute to a holistic understanding of the impacts, challenges, and prospects of open data in Nigeria's development journey. In doing so, it aims to provide valuable insights for policy reform, strategic planning, and decision-making at both governmental and non-governmental levels.

1.2 Problem statement

¹ OGP was established in 2011 as a collaborative endeavor between government leaders and civil society advocates, aimed at fostering transparent, participatory, inclusive, and accountable governance. Currently, it comprises 75 countries, 104 local governments, and numerous civil society organizations. OGP embodies a dynamic global partnership for open governments.

² In September 2013, Edo state in Southern Nigeria launched its own open data portal and became the first sub-national government to operationalize the open data initiative in Western Africa.

Within the Nigerian context, the execution of open data initiatives presents a complex landscape that intertwines technological, operational, legal, political, and socio-economic dimensions. Despite the growing recognition of open data's potential to foster transparency and good governance, challenges persist in effectively harnessing its benefits in the country. The coexistence of data asymmetry, data protection,³ technical limitations, and legal intricacies has led to variations in the accessibility and utility of open data.

The problem at hand is how to navigate these challenges and optimize the influence of open data in Nigeria's development trajectory. While advancements have been made in terms of data dissemination through open data portals, the extent to which these initiatives have translated into substantial gains in transparency, accountability, and socio-economic progress remains a matter of exploration.

1.3 Research purpose

This dissertation aims to investigate the intricacies of open data initiatives within Nigeria's development journey. It seeks to investigate the interplay between open data, transparency, accountability, and good governance while identifying the specific barriers that inhibit the realization of open data's potential.

The research seeks to provide actionable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to strategically address these challenges and create an environment conducive to the effective utilization of open data for sustainable development.

1.4 Research objectives

The research is guided by the following objectives.

- i. To assess the evolution of open data accessibility and availability in Nigeria since 2017.
- ii. To analyze the impact of open data portals in Nigeria on fiscal transparency.
- iii. To uncover the institutional transparency outcomes arising from the implementation of open data initiatives in Nigeria.

³ The Nigeria Data Protection Bureau (NDPB) was established in February 2022. The Bureau is mandated to, inter alia, oversee the implementation of the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR) which was issued by National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) in 2019 as a subsidiary legislation of NITDA Act, 2007 (National Data Protection Commission, NDPC 2023).

- iv. To identify and critically evaluate the key challenges and barriers faced in the integration of open data for advancing good governance in Nigeria.

1.5 Research questions

Based on the research papers examined, here are some questions the research will answer.

- i. Has there been an improvement in the availability and accessibility of open data in Nigeria since 2017?
- ii. To what extent does open data portals in Nigeria promote fiscal transparency?
- iii. What are the institutional transparency outcomes from open data portals in Nigeria?
- iv. What are the main challenges and barriers to implementing open data for good governance in Nigeria?

1.6 Research structure

This dissertation is structured to encompass a comprehensive exploration of the multifaceted aspects of open data within development practices in Nigeria. The subsequent sections will delve into the concepts of open data, transparency, accountability, and good governance, and drawing on a synthesis of scholarly literature. The third section describes method for data collection and sampling while the following section analysis collected data using interface analysis of OGD portals and systemic textual analysis to elucidate on the current landscape and the complexities of open data adoption in Nigeria. The closing section summarizes findings, potential solutions, and opportunities for further studies.

1.7 Contributions to knowledge

While there is existing literature on open data and its potential benefits for development, there are limited research on the execution of open data initiatives in Nigeria and the extent to which open data is being used to promote social accountability, transparency, and good governance.

This dissertation seeks to contribute valuable insights to the academic discourse of open data within the context of development practices. The analysis of various perspectives and challenges related to open data will provide a refined understanding of its impact on transparency, governance, and development outcomes.

Additionally, the research aims to provide recommendations for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers engaged in leveraging open data for effective governance and sustainable development.

2.0 REVIEW OF LITERATURE AND KEY CONCEPTUAL IDEAS

This chapter reviews literature on the concept of open data, transparency, accountability, and good governance, and takes a deep dive into various perspectives of the role that open data plays in development practices.

This literature critically examined the impact of open data in shaping development practices in various countries with specific focus on Nigeria. It revealed a robust link between open data, accountability, transparency, good governance, and development practices.

The chapter concluded that there are various perspectives for examining open data's impact on development practices and each of them comes with its own challenges, but it provides a clearer insight of the role of open data in development practices in contemporary times.

2.1 The concept of open data

Open data is data that is freely available for public use and consumption. According to Goldstein et al. (2013), open data is “data that is freely available for anyone to use, reuse, and redistribute, without restrictions from copyright, patents, or other mechanisms of control.” Other scholars such as Kitchin (2014), Van Schalkwyk et al. (2017), and Davies et al. (2019) also emphasize the importance of open data being easily accessible for use, reuse, and redistribution.

Smith and Seward (2020) provide a more comprehensive understanding of open data, stating that it is data made available by public or private organizations with the aim of promoting transparency, accountability, and collaboration. It is typically provided in a structured, machine-readable format that enables easy access and reuse. Similarly, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2020) defines open data as data made available by governments, organizations, or individuals in a machine-readable format with an open license that allows for reuse and redistribution by others. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2014) emphasized that open data has become an essential tool in evidence-based policy formulation, resource allocation and monitoring development practices and outcomes.

Arguments in favor of open data highlight its role in enhancing democratic processes by providing citizens, civil society organizations, and researchers with access to information about government activities and public services (Goldstein et al., 2013; Kitchin, 2014). Smith and Seward (2020) also argue that open data fosters innovation by providing a wealth of information for the development of new services, products, and solutions to societal challenges.

On the other hand, critics raise concerns about privacy, security, data ownership and control, and the potential misuse of sensitive information (Goldstein et al., 2013; Kitchin, 2014; OECD, 2019a). They caution that open data does not automatically lead to beneficial outcomes that address social and economic inequalities (Davies et al., 2019).

Despite the ongoing debates and arguments, there is a consensus that open data plays a crucial role in development practices by promoting transparency and accountability.

2.2 The concept of transparency

Transparency is defined as the degree to which government activities and decisions are made visible, accessible, and understandable to the public (Bvuma and Joseph, 2019). The UNDP (2022) supports this definition, emphasizing that transparency involves the openness, accessibility, and visibility of government actions, decisions, and information. These characteristics enable citizens to hold public officials accountable and participate in governance processes. Other scholars' definition of transparency focused on ensuring that government actions are visible, predictable, and subject to scrutiny including public expenditures, officials, and institutions (Ganapati et al., 2017; OECD, 2018; Saxena and Muhammad, 2018).

Gurin (2014), Kitchin (2014) and Goldstein et al. (2013) argued in favour of transparency that it enables accountability and encourages citizen engagement when they have access to government data or information on expenditure. The World Bank (2015) corroborated that transparency promotes good governance by providing access to public sector information, such as budgetary allocations, procurement data, and government contracts. Also, transparency when infused with open data stimulates innovation by providing a wealth of information for the development of new services, products, and solutions to societal challenges (Charalabidis et al., 2018; Smith and Seward, 2020).

However, critics of transparency raise concerns about privacy, security, data ownership and control, and the potential misuse of sensitive information (Goldstein et al., 2013; Kitchin, 2014; OECD, 2019a). They also argued that transparency initiatives may worsen inequalities, as marginalized groups may lack the necessary technology or skills to effectively access and utilize transparent information (Davies et al., 2019; Rodríguez Bolívar et al., 2019).

There are diverse types of transparency which include institutional, data, fiscal, corporate, and environmental transparency. Institutional transparency refers to the openness of institutions and organizations, including government agencies, corporations, and non-profit organizations through disclosure of information about their structures, processes, decision-making, and performance (Moore, 2018). Data transparency involves making data accessible, understandable, and usable by the public for critiques, analysis, research, and innovation (Manyika et al., 2013). Meanwhile, fiscal transparency denotes the disclosure and availability of relevant fiscal information, including budgetary allocations, government revenues, expenditures, and public debt, allowing for public scrutiny and accountability (OECD, 2018; Kariuki et al., 2019).

This literature review will primarily focus on institutional, data, and fiscal transparency as they are most relevant to the study. Understanding the transparency of institutions and government agencies through these types of transparency is crucial in assessing their commitment to open data initiatives, the availability of data, and their engagement with citizens and stakeholders.

2.3 Open data and Transparency

Open data serves as a catalyst for transparency in governance, allowing access to government information and empowering citizens to monitor and scrutinize government activities (Charalabidis et al., 2018). There are two sides to transparency: the demand side, which means citizens and stakeholders being able to access and use this information easily, and the supply side, which means the government proactively delivering the information to the public (Araujo and Tejedo-Romero, 2016).

Research conducted by Bvuma and Joseph (2019) on public service delivery in South Africa and Stagars (2016) on Southeast Asia supports the assertion that open data promotes transparency. Bvuma and Joseph (2019) defined open data as the availability

and accessibility of government data to the public. They measured open data based on the extent of government data that is published, the formats in which it is shared, and the ease of access provided to citizens. The authors defined transparency as the degree to which government activities and decisions are made visible, accessible, and understandable to the public. Open data was found to contribute to transparency by providing citizens with access to information about government programs, policies, and performance. The study also showed that open data promotes transparency by enabling citizens to participate in decision-making processes. According to Bvuma and Joseph (2019), when citizens have access to government data, they can actively engage in discussions, provide feedback, and contribute to the formulation and evaluation of policies and services.

However, it is important to note that the mere availability and accessibility of open data does not guarantee transparency (Bannister and Connolly, 2011; Roy, 2014). Factors such as data quality, completeness, and timeliness can significantly impact the effectiveness of open data initiatives in achieving transparency goals. Wang and Shepherd (2020) also highlight limitations in granularity and relevance of available data, which can hinder transparency efforts, as observed in the case of open government datasets in the UK.

In Mexico, open government data has been instrumental in increasing transparency and improving public administration, with initiatives such as the use of open contracting data standard (OCDS) for public procurement transparency and accountability (OECD, 2018). Similarly, Australia has enacted the Data Availability and Transparency Act 2022, which allows accredited data users and custodians to enter into data sharing agreements for projects serving the public interest (Australian Government Productivity Commission, 2023).

2.4 The role of open data in development practices

The role of open data in development practices has been a topic of extensive research and debates, it has formed the basis for intellectual arguments about transparency in government. Zuiderwijk et al. (2014, p.2) identified seven different perspectives of OGD research such as political, social, economic, institutional, operational, legal, and technical perspectives and argues that “combining these perspectives may be more effective in dealing with the issues related to open data and stimulating innovation.” The authors simply pointed out that when you examine open data using these multifaceted perspectives will give a better understanding of development outcomes and practices.

Premised on this assertion, I will look at some of the arguments that argue for and against the role that open data plays in development and governance from the perspectives described by Zuiderwijk.

One of the key arguments in favour of open data roles in development practices is its potential to enhance transparency and accountability in governance. Scholars such as Gurin (2014) explained that open data from the perspectives of economic growth and societal challenges enables citizens to monitor government activities, detect corruption, and hold public officials accountable. Kitchin (2014) and Goldstein (2013) corroborated Gurin's line of argument stating that open data enables citizens to access and scrutinize information and data provided by the government and its agencies.

Charalabidis et al. (2018, p.4) stated that open data also plays a crucial role in fostering innovation and driving economic growth. The author's book points out that open data can fuel entrepreneurial activities, stimulate the development of new services and products, and create economic opportunities. Similarly, Smith and Seward (2020) and Kitchin (2014) stated that the wealth of information provided through open data is enough to develop new services, products, and proffer solutions to societal challenges. Additionally, open data enables governments to identify areas of inequality, develop targeted policies, and monitor progress towards sustainable development goals (Davies et al., 2019; Gurin et al., 2014).

Case studies examining open data initiatives in various countries have shown that it enhances public service delivery, fiscal transparency, accountability, and citizen participation (Mejabi et al., 2014, 2017; Stagars, 2016; Kariuki et al., 2019; Bvuma and Joseph, 2019; Ricker et al., 2020). However, there is a need for increased data accessibility, particularly in African countries.

Critics of open government data have raised concerns about privacy, security, data ownership and control, and the potential misuse of sensitive information (Goldstein et al., 2013; Kitchin, 2014; Davies et al., 2019; OECD, 2019a). They have also highlighted the challenge of accessibility, as marginalized groups may lack the necessary technology or skills to effectively utilize open data, limiting its potential for development outcomes (Davies et al., 2019; Rodríguez Bolívar et al., 2019).

To summarize, the arguments regarding the role of open data in development practices revolve around the potential benefits of transparency, accountability, innovation, economic growth, and addressing societal challenges. The literature examined the role of open data from the perspectives of political, economic, social, institutional, operational, and legal perspectives. The findings of the literature also included concerns about data privacy, quality, inclusivity, and accessibility, then, recommended that striking a balance between openness and responsible data practices is essential for effective development practices.

In understanding how open data is significant to development practices, I will be doing an analysis of how it catalyzes accountability and makes the case for fiscal transparency in government.

2.5 Open data and Accountability

Open data has emerged as a catalyst for accountability, enabling citizens to access and analyze government information (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014). It offers opportunities for enhancing accountability mechanisms by providing citizens with access to financial information and enabling them to monitor government expenditures and hold officials accountable (Kariuki et al., 2019; Van Loenen et al., 2018; Van Loenen, 2018). However, challenges such as data privacy, security, and quality still need to be addressed (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014).

New Zealand and China have demonstrated positive progress in using open data for accountability purposes (OECD, 2019b, 2019c). In Ghana, the establishment of the Ghana Open Data Initiative (GODI) demonstrates the government's commitment to open data, but issues regarding public accountability persist due to capacity limitations in audit committees and citizens' complaint centers (Open Government Partnership, OGP 2022). The case of American local governments highlights the need for improved citizen engagement and feedback mechanisms in open data initiatives (Zanmiller, 2015). Similarly, in Canada, there is a growing demand for the application of transparency, accountability, and citizen participation principles to open data for the benefit of citizens (Government of Canada, 2022).

2.6 Fiscal transparency and good governance

Fiscal transparency refers to the extent to which a government provides accurate, comprehensive, and timely information on its fiscal policies, activities, and outcomes (Ganapati et al., 2017). Fiscal transparency is deemed a core element of good governance as its primary goal is to guarantee transparency in government decision-making and public spending.

Developed countries have long recognized the importance of fiscal transparency, with freedom of information legislation mandating it since World War II (Ganapati et al., 2017). In Sub-Saharan African countries, the adoption of fiscal transparency gained prominence in the late twentieth century, partly influenced by the conditionalities imposed by external donors (Crawford and Abdulai, 2009; Mkandawire, 2010).

Scholars have argued that transparency plays a crucial role in promoting good governance by fostering accountability, improving decision-making, encouraging citizen participation, building trust, and ensuring efficient resource allocation. Transparency encourages citizen engagement and participation in governance processes as it allows them access to information about government activities and decisions. Hence, citizens of these countries are more likely to actively participate in public discourse, provide feedback, and contribute to policy formulation (Kitchin, 2014; UNDP, 2022). Goldstein et al. (2013) posits that when government activities are transparent, there is a greater likelihood of identifying and addressing corruption, inefficiencies, and misuse of power. Also, in a polity where government actions and information are transparent, policymakers gain better insight into public needs and priorities, leading to more effective and targeted policies (World Bank, 2015). The strongest argument for transparency is that it contributes to building public trust between the government and its citizens. Transparent governance processes build confidence among citizens that their government and its institutions are acting in their best interests, leading to a stronger social contract and greater public support for governance initiatives (OECD, 2018).

In 2009, the Metropolitan Council in Louisville, USA passed a financial transparency ordinance. This ordinance established the guidelines that the transparency website to publish detailed expenditure information for the various programs in the Metro Government. Though there were issues with data interpretation at the onset but with time, it got better. Currently, the data portal features unprocessed datasets covering city expenditures, employee salaries, board members, park locations and amenities, animal

services population results, news and calendar events, and links to other sites with useful data and maps (Reno-Weber and Niblock, 2013).

Several countries have implemented fiscal transparency initiatives, not only to enhance their international reputation but also for internal control purposes. Brazil's Transparency Portal, which launched in 2004 was initially aimed to track federal money transfers to cities and states. Over time, the Portal expanded its scope, providing information on various aspects such as elected officials' credit card records and World Cup funding, effectively monitoring over \$12 trillion in government funds. Similarly, Slovenia's Commission for the Prevention of Corruption developed the Supervizor application, which offers information on government financial transactions to civil society and government authorities. On its first day, Supervizor received 2 million hits and was later recognized with the UN Public Service Award (World Bank, 2015). These initiatives show the positive impact of fiscal transparency on good governance.

2.7 Open data and good governance

The integration of open data into governance processes has been driven by the recognition of its potential to enhance good governance, with a particular focus on government transparency and accountability (Mutuku and Idriss, 2019).

The use of open data in developed countries has demonstrated its positive influence on good governance. For instance, the United Kingdom has been a lead in open data initiatives, leveraging data transparency to promote citizen engagement, improve public services, and enhance government accountability (Vancauwenberghe and Fawcett, 2018). Similarly, the United States has embraced open data to increase government transparency, empower citizens, and foster innovation through collaborative problem-solving (Bannister and Connolly, 2011). Germany has established the Open Data Portal, enabling citizens to access and analyze government data, fostering transparency and participatory governance (Charalabidis et al., 2018). In Canada, the Open Government initiative has emphasized the importance of open data in raising transparency, citizen engagement, and evidence-based policy making (Government of Canada, 2022). Furthermore, countries like South Korea and Japan have embraced open data to enhance government efficiency, citizen participation, and service delivery (Kim et al., 2017; OECD, 2019d).

In Sub-Saharan African countries, open data initiatives are still in its early stages of adoption, but there is growing recognition of its potential to contribute to good governance. Governments in the region are increasingly acknowledging the need for accountability and transparency in public administration, and open data is perceived as a conduit for accomplishing these objectives (Mutuku and Idriss, 2019; Mejabi, 2017; Kariuki, 2019). However, challenges such as limited technical capacity, inadequate data infrastructure, and weak institutional frameworks hinder the effective implementation of open data for promoting good governance in Sub-Saharan Africa (Mutuku and Idriss, 2019; Crawford and Abdulai, 2009).

2.8 Summary of reviewed literature

Open data has made a significant contribution to the landscape of development practices across the globe. While the comprehensive review of pertinent literature relating to open data provides evidence-based and multidimensional insights of these impacts, the authors also dived into some challenges of open data from various perspectives.

Bannister and Connolly (2011) and Mayernik (2017) emphasize the correlation between open data and increased transparency, subsequently leading to improved governance. Open data initiatives have enabled citizens to scrutinize government actions, detect corruption, and hold officials accountable, thereby enhancing political transparency and citizen engagement. From a political perspective, open data is still susceptible to lack of political will by government officials and agencies to share critical information (Gurin, 2014) and in some cases, political manipulation, where government uses data to project an image of transparency while concealing more sensitive or controversial information (Goldstein et al., 2013).

Saxena and Muhammad (2018) and Davies et al. (2019) opined that open data has empowered citizens and CSOs to demand accountability from their governments while marginalized groups now have access to data that will drive social equity and inclusivity. However, the authors shared their concerns regarding digital divide in the societies, data bias, data literacy, lack of standardization, and privacy concerns (Manyika et al., 2019; Goldstein et al., 2013)

The potential for open data to fuel innovation and economic growth is highlighted by Charalabidis et al. (2018) and Smith and Seward (2020). Open data serves as a rich resource for entrepreneurs to develop new services, products, and solutions, fostering economic advancement. The challenges of open data from an economic perspective highlight the social impacts of the data to drive societal change and the resource constraints encountered by government statistical agencies.

Ganapati et al., 2017 stated that open data platforms enhance institutional transparency by allowing public access to government data. However, challenges persist regarding data accuracy and relevance (Bvuma and Joseph, 2019), even Moore (2018) stress the necessity of well-defined disclosure mechanisms to ensure the credibility of institutional transparency. Also, from operational and technical perspectives, open data has its own challenges such as inadequate technical expertise and infrastructure, lack of interdepartmental collaboration, data format and standardization, user engagement and accessibility, data quality and accuracy, and sustainability (Bannister and Connolly, 2011; Bvuma and Joseph, 2019; Mayernik, 2017).

From a legal perspective, open government partnerships is getting more institutional backing with laws and acts being passed at all levels. However, the execution of open data initiatives presents a range of legal challenges relating to data ownership complexities, privacy concerns, intellectual property rights, licensing, and cross-border issues (Goldstein et al., 2013; Kitchin, 2014; OECD, 2019a; UNESCO, 2020).

Open data has brought about positive transformations across political, social, economic, institutional, operational, technical, and legal dimensions of development. However, it also faces challenges such as political manipulation, digital divides, data quality, and legal intricacies. The reviewed literature underscores the multidimensional impact of open data and provides a foundation for understanding its role in contemporary development practices.

3.0 DESCRIPTION OF METHODS AND SAMPLING

This chapter explains the approach, sampling technique and methods of data collection and analysis used in the study. The qualitative approach which was used in the study will be explained in detail below. Also, the qualitative approach favoured exploratory, descriptive, structured interview and data portal analysis for the study.

For this research, the sample size was narrowed down to stakeholders in charge of collecting the data, analyzing, and publishing it on OGD portals and the users of open data such as the CSOs and think tanks. Structured interview was the preferred method of data collection for this study, especially the primary data. The research was conducted using non-probability sampling technique, snowball sampling. For secondary data collection, they were gathered from several open data portals in Nigeria and other verifiable data sources within the country.

3.1 Study approach

The qualitative approach was used to analyze the impact of open data on development practices with central focus on data availability, accessibility, and quality and how it [data] contributes to transparency, accountability, and good governance in Nigeria. To achieve this, the research instrument used is targeted interviews of: government MDAs in charge of collecting, analyzing, and publishing OGD; and the users such as CSOs and the public.

The interviews are the primary data source used for this study while secondary data was obtained from observing the OGD portals which are frequented or mostly used by CSOs and the public. The two data sources will be extrapolated using systematic textual analysis aided by NVivo to map out similarities, differences, and drawbacks of open data in Nigeria and how it impacts development practices.

The study was exploratory and descriptive to reveal impacts of open data on development practices in Nigeria. The exploratory part which has been carried out during the literature review and explaining conceptual ideas explored aspects open data, development practices, accountability, transparency, good governance. Descriptive strategy was also employed to elucidate the functionality of open data in development practices. However, to determine the extent of open data impact in development practices within Nigerian context, the research used structured interview with key persons working with OGD and

analysis of open data portals in Nigeria were carried out. The analysis and discussion of findings section will show an analysis of some major open data portals using interface analysis and how the data collected from the interviews were collated, sectioned, and analyzed using systematic textual analysis aided by NVivo.

3.2 Sampling technique

The sample size was narrowed down to stakeholders in charge of collecting the data, analyzing, and publishing it on OGD portals and the users of open data such as the CSOs. This research was conducted using non-probability sampling technique, snowball sampling.

Snowball sampling was decided on with due to the complexities of getting Nigerian federal civil servants to interview, considering the recent change in government and the bureaucracy around interviewing civil servants in Nigeria. This sampling technique is also beneficial for the users of open data such as the CSOs to reach those who mine or request open data from the federal government to track and monitor their accountability and transparency.

3.3 Data collection

Being qualitative research, structured interview was the preferred method of data collection for this study which would serve as the primary data. The Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget and National Planning and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) were identified as the major government ministries. Key personnels from these MDAs in charge of government data and finances will be interviewed.

Another source of primary data are the CSOs who mine or request open data from the federal government to track and monitor their accountability and transparency. Key CSOs such as BudgIT and Connected Development (CODE) that have deep roots in advocacy for transparency, accountability and good governance, and an independent non-profit think tank, Ominira Initiative for Economic Advancement were identified. Personnels from these CSOs who worked closely with open data and interfaced with Nigeria MDAs were interviewed for this study.

In reaching out to potential respondents from the MDAs, informal contact persons were used including junior staff at the ministries or direct contact through LinkedIn. Then,

respondents from the identified CSOs were reached out to using indirect and direct contact persons and official interview schedules were setup and carried out.

The questionnaire design used for interview with these respondents was edited multiple times to suit the research questions for this study. Then, a pilot interview session with a staff of Ominira Initiative was carried out with the edited questionnaire and the outcome of the interview led to more edits of the questionnaire. The final copy of the questionnaire was subsequently used in interviewing respondents from BudgIT and CODE.

For secondary data collection, they were gathered from several open data portals in Nigeria, OGP Nigeria National Action Plan from 2017 to 2025 and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) portal.

3.4 Data analysis

This study draws on the work of Gray (2023) that explores three approaches for studying the social life of data portals as technopolitical devices using interface, software, and metadata analysis. These approaches shed light on data portals as complex and evolving spaces of public sector data involvement, aiding the evaluation of participation mechanisms and prompting a reconsideration of their structure (Gray, 2023).

However, this study will only use interface analysis to examine some major open data portals in Nigeria such as the Open Treasury portal, Nigeria Open Contracting Portal (NOCOPO), the Budget Office of the Federation's (BOF) website, and the NBS website.

I will be analyzing the primary data obtained from the interviews using systematic textual analysis. This data analysis method encompasses systemic linguistic examination and intertextual analysis. Systemic linguistic analysis delves into multifunctional language analysis, offering a holistic portrayal of discursive practices and socio-cognitive representations. Intertextual analysis draws cognitive connections between prior discursive histories and contemporary discourse. This will be aided by transcription of the interviews and put through NVivo software to highlight similarities, differences, and drawbacks of open data in Nigeria and how it impacts development practices.

4.0 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter provides an analysis of the major open government data portals in Nigeria using interface analysis. Such an analysis is important for an advanced understanding of how OGD portals in Nigeria are improving user accessibility with their interface. It also reveals how these data portal interfaces contribute to participation or usage of published data with the way it is organized or presented on the portal.

Then, this chapter will corroborate the findings from OGD portal with analysis of the primary data obtained from the interviews using systematic textual analysis. The aim of this chapter is to see how open data within the Nigerian context is impacting on development practices.

The chapter is divided into five sections, each presenting distinct aspects of findings grouped as analysis of OGD portals, thematization of participant positions which is a further intertextual discussion of the analysis and summary of findings. The last two sections shed light on the limitations of the research and implications for policy.

4.1 OGD portals

Since 2016 when Nigeria joined OGP, it has developed three action plans: 2017-2019, 2019-2022 and 2023-2025. The OGP Nigeria National Action Plan (2017-2019) proposed four commitments such as fiscal transparency, anti-corruption, access to information and citizen engagement and empowerment (OGP, 2017).

While implementing the first OGP action plan, the Bureau of Public Procurement (BPP) used its momentum to realise one of the core requirements contained in the Public Procurement Act 2007. It is required that the BPP establish a single internet portal that serves as a primary and definitive source of all information on government procurement, which contains and displays all public sector procurement information. In April 2018, the BPP announced that the Nigerian Open Contracting Portal (NOCOPO) will go live in May (Sahara Reporters, 2018).

The OGP midterm independent reporting mechanism (IRM) spotlighted the launch of the portal and the challenges in its adoption due to limited uploaded information (OGP, 2023). Five years after its launch, here is an interface analysis of the NOCOPO website, www.nocopo.bpp.gov.ng.

Welcome To The Official Nigeria Open Contracting Portal (NOCOPO)

Track and manage contracts files of the federal government of Nigeria

search

search for any project data

84,420

Planned Projects Count

15,479

Awarded Projects Count

3,220T+

Total Projects in Naira

23,691

Published Projects Count

All Projects And Fund Allocation

Source: NOCOPO website

According to Gray (2023), one of the prominent feature of data portal interfaces is usage stats related to data portal activity such as total datasets, APIs, downloads, site visitors, downloads, discussion thread numbers, counts of contributing bodies, and numbers of blog posts, apps, visualizations, and data requests. As shown in the screenshot of the

NOCOPO above, it shows stats of planned projects, awarded projects, total projects in naira, and published projects count contained in the portal.

Source: NOCOPO website

The use of the keyword ‘construction,’ in the search engine produced results of procurements relating to construction with headings such as open contract identity (OCID) code, project title, date published, package number, lot number, budget year for the procurement and download action. I proceeded to download some of the projects on the search results and it downloaded as a .JSON file.

Source: NOCOPO website

The .JSON file stores data in key-value pairs and arrays. I was unable to open the downloaded file with the applications on my laptop, however, using chrome browser showed a block of code that would be unreadable to a layman.

```
{
  "uri": "http://nocopo.bpp.gov.ng/ocdsjson.ashx?ocid=ocds-gy166f-111001001-000001",
  "version": "1.1",
  "publishedDate": "2021-05-03T21:45:00Z",
  "releases": [
    {
      "ocid": "ocds-gy166f-111001001-000001",
      "id": "818",
      "date": "2021-05-03T21:45:00Z",
      "tag": [
        "planning"
      ],
      "initiationType": "tender",
      "parties": [
        {
          "name": "STATE HOUSE - HQTRS",
          "id": "NG-BPP-BPP-NOC-111001001",
          "identifier": {
            "scheme": "NG-BPP",
            "id": "BPP-NOC-111001001",
            "legalName": "STATE HOUSE - HQTRS"
          },
          "roles": [
            "buyer",
            "payer",
            "procuringEntity"
          ]
        },
        {
          "id": "NG-BPP-BPP-NOC-111001001",
          "name": "STATE HOUSE - HQTRS",
          "planning": {
            "rationale": "Reconstruction and Furnishing the Security Building within the Villa including Extension od Bodyguard",
            "budget": {
              "id": "818",
              "description": "ERGP14101515",
              "amount": {
                "amount": 42628061.0000,
                "currency": "NGN"
              },
              "project": "Reconstruction and Furnishing the Security Building within the Villa including Extension od Bodyguard",
              "projectID": "6922",
              "milestones": [
                {
                  "id": "2341",
                  "title": "Advert of Expression of Interest",
                  "description": "Advert of Expression of Interest for Reconstruction and Furnishing the Security Building within the Villa including Extension od Bodyguard",
                  "code": "preProcurement",
                  "status": "met"
                },
                {
                  "id": "2342",
                  "title": "Request for proposal ",
                  "description": "Invitation for request for proposal for Reconstruction and Furnishing the Security Building within the Villa including Extension od Bodyguard",
                  "code": "preProcurement",
                  "status": "met"
                }
              ],
              "language": "en"
            },
            "publisher": {
              "name": "The Bureau of Public Procurement",
              "scheme": "NG-BPP",
              "uid": "BPP-01",
              "license": "http://nocopo.bpp.gov.ng/license",
              "publicationPolicy": "http://nocopo.bpp.gov.ng/policy"
            }
          }
        }
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

Source: NOCOPO website

Manovich (2008) posits that reading portal aesthetics and interface conventions starts from the search bars; icons indicating different data topics; graphs, charts, and visualizations; and content boxes with photos, blog posts, and other news and updates. But this is slightly different with the NOCOPO website. For instance, the NOCOPO portal user accreditation interface for citizens; CSOs; procuring entities; suppliers, contractors, and consultants; and the private sector revealed a lack of accessibility. When you click on the ‘proceed’ for citizens you are met with a block of code which reads, ‘Server Error in '/noc' Application,’ but other user portals take you to a login page.

Source: NOCOPO website

The NOCOPO website interface is quite thin and scanty, despite holding the combined database to all government procurement in Nigeria.

Another major OGD portal in Nigeria is the open treasury website. It was launched by President Buhari in December 219, the website www.opentreasury.gov.ng was created to publicize treasury statement on how monies that come into government coffer are being spent daily. Federal government MDAs are required to routinely release reports detailing payments exceeding N5 million, monthly budget performance, and various other official financial transactions (The Punch, 2019).

The homepage of the website has graph slideshows at the center of the website showing the budget performance by administrative segments and by functions of government. At the left side of the graph slideshows, there is the ‘report’ tagline, there are daily, monthly, quarterly, and annual report of financial and treasury statements from the federal government and its MDAs including the tab on COVID-19 reports from federal and state governments.

Source: Open Treasury Website

The data contained on the website begins in 2018, which tallies with the period the website was in beta testing till it was eventually launched in 2019. However, the annual general purpose financial statement has report as far back as 2013.

Daily Treasury Statement (FGN) 2018

Date	Excel format
01/10/2018	download
02/10/2018	download
03/10/2018	download
04/10/2018	download
05/10/2018	download
06/10/2018	download
07/10/2018	download
08/10/2018	download
09/10/2018	download
10/10/2018	download

Source: Open Treasury Website

A look at the federal government daily treasury statements for October 2018 revealed missing data from eight days which were weekends when government offices are closed as depicted in the screenshot above. When I clicked on some of the data years, including 2023, it bounced back to the homepage, especially for daily reports which means some of the data have not been uploaded to the website.

The screenshot shows a modal window with a close button (X) in the top right corner. Inside the modal, there are nine green buttons arranged in a 3x3 grid, labeled with the years 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024, 2025, and 2026. The background page is dimmed and shows a sidebar with 'REPORTS' and 'Daily Treasury Statement' selected. The main content area has a title 'BUDGET PERFORMANCE BY ADMINISTRATIVE SEGEMENTS - FIRST (1ST) QUARTER 2020' and a chart area.

Source: Open Treasury Website

The portal which has been setup to track daily treasury and payments of the Nigerian government is not updated neither daily, weekly, monthly nor yearly. In 2021, it was reported that the open treasury portal was shutdown (Udegbunam and Igwe, 2021), when it was restored the financial statements of the Office of the Accountant General of the Federation (OAGF), the Nigerian Army (NA) and the Nigerian Navy (NN) were not fully disclosed on the portal (Daily Trust, 2022) with several reports of payment without descriptions and beneficiary names contained on the portal (Olawoyin, 2020; Daily Trust, 2022).

The Budget Office of the Federation (BOF) is within the Ministry of Finance, Budget, and National Planning. It was established to provide budget functions such as preparation of executive budget, oversee its implementation, and monitor the budget. The website www.budgetoffice.gov.ng has an interactive interface with well-defined categories as seen in the screenshot below and it is one of the major data portals for tracking fiscal transparency in Nigeria.

Source: BOF Website

A click on the resources tab, then internal resources take you to budget documents which has the database of Nigerian budget from 2009 and usually contains documents such as budget call circular and ends with appropriation bill signed by the president and supplementary budget details for each fiscal year.

Budget Document

2023 Budget (56 Documents)	2022 Budget (57 Documents)	2021 Budget (29 Documents)
2020 Budget (65 Documents)	2019 Budget (15 Documents)	2018 Budget (8 Documents)
2017 Budget (38 Documents)	2017 Approved Budget (42 Documents)	2016 Budget (41 Documents)
2015 Budget (58 Documents)	2014 Budget (57 Documents)	2013 Budget (56 Documents)
2012 Budget (41 Documents)	2011 Budget (60 Documents)	2010 Budget (55 Documents)
2009 Budget (51 Documents)		

Source: BOF website

As seen on the website, there are topical directories that guide citizens on how to understand the budget, budget timelines, key facts, documents, policy documents, implementation performance, i-Monitor budget and so on. Neurath and Kinross (2009) opined that visual icons are abstracted, encyclopedic, simplified, minimal, accessible visual depictions of different areas of institutional work and complement search interfaces.

Source: BOF Website

All these visual icons which are contained in the citizens' portal tab have video explainers, PDF files documents with simplified infographics to help citizens understand

budget information. However, the links to implementation performance and i-monitor budget usually bounces back as error command, ‘404 not found.’

Source: BOF website

Meanwhile, other visual icons on the website shows an array of other accessibility features such as the register participants icon—though duplicated—is for MDAs to register for the 2024 budget preparation workshop, the helpdesk to seek help in navigating the website and the mail icon is for budget office staff mail. There

The NBS manages and publishes statistics for Nigeria which makes it a major open data point in the country. It was established with the Statistics Act of 2007 and led to the merger of the Federal Office of Statistics (FOS) and the National Data Bank (NDB).

Source: NBS website

The website, www.nigerianstat.gov.ng is a national data bank that shows recently published data such as inflation rate, foreign trade statistics, unemployment data, oil prices in Nigeria, gross domestic product (GDP) and other data. It also has categories that focus on poverty maps and COVID-19 data hub.

The data warehouse on the NBS website shows the open data portal for Nigeria with short data profile for all the thirty-six states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). The open data portal contains social data including census data and the national summary data page (NSDP). It also has the National Data Archive (NADA) Centre containing several surveys carried out by the NBS. The health atlas link on the data warehouse takes you to Nigeria social statistics atlas with database on state health atlas, education, labour and gender statistics, and expenditures on health and major outcomes. The foreign trade monitor app shows Nigeria's trade data and map. There are also links that take you to the NBS mobile apps where you can access these data on your phones and iPads.

Source: NBS website

The NBS also has a data release calendar for publishing its data. The calendar guides the work of the NBS especially when it comes to monthly data on Consumer Price Index (CPI) and inflation report, food price watch, federation account allocation committee (FAAC), and quarterly and annual data on trade, value added tax (VAT), GDP, and labour force.

Source: NBS website

An interface analysis of the NBS website revealed that it is easy to navigate, and the published data is presented using infographics and the reports on the e-library as shown in the screenshots comes with an executive summary, and option to download the PDF report, excel tables or JPEG infographics.

Source: NBS website

 Company Income Tax Q2 2023

Executive Summary

On the aggregate, Company Income Tax (CIT) for Q2 2023 was reported at N1.53 trillion, indicating a growth rate of 226.40% on a quarter-on-quarter basis from N469.01 billion in Q1 2023. Local payments received were N1.02 trillion, while Foreign CIT Payment contributed N505.91 billion in Q2 2023. On a quarter-on-quarter basis, water supply, sewerage, waste management, and remediation activities recorded the highest growth rate with 626.52%, followed by accommodation and food service activities with 585.11%. On the other hand, education had the lowest growth rate with - 15.48%, followed by public administration and defence, compulsory social security with 25.46%. In terms of sectoral contributions, the top three largest shares in Q2 2023 were manufacturing with 25.63%; financial and insurance activities with 24.47%; and information and communication with 20.30%. However, the activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of households for own use recorded the least share with 0.01%, followed by activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies with 0.06%; and water supply, sewerage, waste management, and remediation activities with 0.09%. In addition, on a year-on-year basis, CIT collections in Q2 2023 increased by 114.28% from Q2 2022.

Data source: National Bureau of Statistics

 [Download Tables](#)

INFOGRAPHICS

Source: NBS website

Overall, the analyses of open data portals in Nigeria revealed that there is constitutional and legal backing for the creation of OGD portals and some of these portals have been launched and functional. However, there are still cases of missing and dormant links on the portal websites, lack of constant updates on the open-source portals as seen on NOCOPO and Open Treasury Portal. These data portals are in fulfillment of the commitments to the OGP action plan, however, there are still data asymmetry and protection issues, and technical limitations of OGD portals in Nigeria (Udegbonam and Igwe, 2021; Daily Trust, 2022). The interface analysis of these portals shows there are still data accessibility issues for users as some of the portals are not easy to navigate and poor internet connections could delay the access to these data portals. Some of the portals are not user-friendly, for instance the NOCOPO with the preferred download format and long process to register on the portal. The portals which are user-friendly have data asymmetry issues like the open treasury portal and budget office portal. However, the OGD portals in Nigeria are reshaping developmental practices by providing information and data relevant to citizens' lives and the economy but there remain challenges in their quest to make data open, accessible, and available.

4.2 Thematization of participant positions

I had interviews with two CSO staff, BudgIT and Connected Development (CODE), and the executive director of a think tank organization, Ominira Initiative for Economic Advancement (Ominira). These interviews took place virtually using my UEA Microsoft Teams account to conduct the interview, the interviews were recorded and transcribed

with the permission of the interviewee. The transcript of the interviews was edited and imported into NVivo where it was coded and analyzed using themes such as data accessibility, data availability, data monitoring, data visualization, data protection, data quality, data use, missing data, accountability, transparency, good governance, advocacy, open data challenges, freedom of information (FOI)⁴, and advocacy. Below is a summary of the percentage coverages for these themes from each interview.

Figure 1: NVivo percentage coverage of themes from interview with BudGIT

Figure 2: NVivo percentage coverage of themes from interview with CODE

⁴ The Freedom of Information Act 2011 grants individuals and organizations the right to request information, regardless of its format, that is held by any public official, agency, or institution, regardless of its description (Agba et al., 2018).

Figure 3: NVivo percentage coverage of themes from interview with Ominira

Figure 4: NVivo's number of coding references by themes

4.2.1 Data accessibility

Nigeria as a signatory to OGP implemented a national action plan with a major thematic focus on ‘access to information.’ During interviews with respondents, I posed questions on data accessibility in Nigeria.

While one interviewee stated that “there is no central pool for government data to be accessed in Nigeria” (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14), another interviewee opined that “Sometimes it is a lack of knowledge. They don't know that it exists while other times, it is a matter of the data not even being there. So, they just do not know that it exists or not just paying attention” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22). However, a central point on data accessibility is that when the data are made available, “datasets are sometimes not in machine readable format” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22).

Then, another interviewee stated that “some of the MDAs have not streamlined their activities or gone digital, they still prefer pushing physical papers which affects accessing data from their MDAs” (Interviewee 1, personal communication, August 4). Findings from a study conducted by Ezema (2023) examining thirty-four government agencies found that only 26.5 percent of these agencies have government research data on their websites while two of the agencies have no official and functional websites.

4.2.2 Data availability

Government data in Nigeria is plagued with availability issues, despite the NBs having a data release calendar. One of the interviewees stated that “Data are not up to date. They do not come out in time. You want to analyze something for the first quarter, and you are getting the information or data in the third quarter” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22). Though, one interviewee pointed out that “there is a sort of improvement in data availability for NOCOPO which is being updated on daily basis, but it is not sufficient. The portals are not running the way we want, we want to see everything [data] available” (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14).

4.2.3 Data monitoring

In this context, data monitoring talks about how open data has helped CSOs create advocacy policies around confirming budgeted figures and projects. The release of budget

documents by the federal government has led to the development of project monitoring initiatives such as BudgIT's Tracka and CODE's Follow The Money. An instance of using data for project monitoring was explained by an interviewee:

“When we do data mining, we look at data released by the government on the budget document and NOCOPO portal. We see that the government has budgeted this amount for a project and release of funds has been done by confirming on NOCOPO, so we focus on tracking its implementation. We will verify that this project has a tender document, and check whether the community exists, and the place where the project is being executed exists. And that is when we try to engage community members to work with the verified data and let them know that the government has already put it up to say we are calling for a bidding process and they can follow the process” (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14).

This was corroborated by another interviewee, who stated that:

“The budget runs on a calendar year in Nigeria and senators nominate project to be done in their constituencies slated as constituency projects. Most of the time that is where we start our tracking. We get a list of all those things that have been nominated by the senators and verify if these projects are being done or does the money release tally with budget allocation” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22).

Open data monitoring has also sparked the calls for more advocacy to increase data availability, this was the notion of an interviewee, who stated that:

“In 2020, NBS published a data saying that about over 70 percent of landlords do not have land titles in Nigeria. This made me realize that there is the need to advocate for establishing property rights and increasing land registrations to protect landowners. This is because we datainterpreted that data, realized that there is a problem there that needs to be solved. This is where we got the idea to start a project that focuses on increased land registration in the country” (Interviewee 1, personal communication, August 4).

4.2.4 Data visualization

For a government data portal, data visualization is a key aspect when creating the website. Nayek's (2018) study of OGD websites across all continents of the world found that out of six portals examined, some of them provided visualization features, from limited basic charts and maps to advanced charting and visualization. The interviewees who spoke with me on OGD talked about data visualization of these government websites, one said that: "Sometimes most of these data are not really visualized to the understanding of a layman on the street" (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14). On observation, some of the websites examined using interface analysis corroborated that data visualization for Nigerian OGD websites are poor compared to other United Kingdom, United States and Canada OGD with advanced charting and visualization.

However, another interviewee opined that "MDAs with OGD portals are paying more attention to how they represent data. They are also tending to improve and start to give machine readable data and open to feedback" (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22). This is evident in the case of NBS portal which has a real-time visualization of published data on crude oil price tracking, GDP, CPI, unemployment, and foreign trade (NBS, 2023).

4.2.5 Data protection and privacy

Open data has opened the globe to data protection and privacy issues. Three months ago, Nigeria's President Bola Tinubu signed the Data Protection Bill into law (Premium Times, 2023). In September 2022, the bill was introduced to the country's national assembly when the NDPC (formerly NDPB) sought legal backing, in line with Nigeria's Digital Identification for Development Project.⁵ The Data Protection Act, 2023, incorporates widely recognized data protection principles and covers a broad definition of personal data. Nigeria is keeping up with international standards to protect user data and information. With the NDPC leading the charge with a mandate to hold government MDAs accountable over any data breach (Tunji, 2023).

⁵ The World Bank funded project is aimed at increasing the number of persons with a national identification number (NIN), issued by a robust and inclusive foundational ID system, that facilitates their access to services.

Within this context, when we posed questions regarding data protection and privacy to interviewees, they revealed that as a CSO, they continue to promote digital rights and privacy. According to an interviewee: “We do not sell data. Our work is open through Creative Commons Licenses. We do not use data and personal information given to us by people who subscribe to our newsletter to send unsolicited messages. And we ensure that all the data is kept safe through our Google Suite” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22).

On same issue, another interviewee stated that:

“We have thematic areas in our organization such as basic education, basic health, water, and sanitation. We do not monitor allocations for military procurement or national security issues. All the data we get regarding these thematic areas is meant for the public, we simplify and present it to the public. For instance, there is no personal information on NOCOPO platform, all information on it is meant for public consumption (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14).

4.2.6 Data quality

In measuring how well Nigerian government websites provides data are accurate, complete, valid, consistent, unique, timely and fit for purpose, I posed questions to my interviewees on data quality. A respondent said, “data quality has improved over the last ten years through technology, most Nigerian MDA have had to digitize their data and process” (Interviewee 1, personal communication, August 4). Another interviewee stated that, “there is a lot of improvement when it comes to how we access the data, it has become an open government thing in some agency, while at times, it has to do with political priority” (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14). In this context, he opined that some MDAs have made data availability and access into a political priority thing, especially when you request for data to monitor a project already slated in the budget.

From a broader perspective on data quality, an interviewee said, “When we get data from the government, we give them some level of credence for the data they are releasing to us. When we see that there are some shortfalls from the information released, we try to draw

their attention to it” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22). Also, the timeliness of data continues to be a huge issue for OGD portals.

4.2.7 Data use

In this context, data use focuses on how data from OGD is being used by the public and CSOs. “Without these datasets, we basically cannot do anything,” this is a respondent said when I enquired about the importance of OGD. When probed further, the interviewee said:

“We translate this data into an infographic, animations, cartoons, write policy notes and other medium so that ordinary people can understand the importance of what those data means. This helps us to break it down for the Nigerian population and to let them understand how these resources are being expended, and this has led to conversations that make sense at the end of the day because citizens are starting to ask questions” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22).

Another interviewee said, “We use OGD to do advocacy and track. We simplify those documents in a way every citizen can be able to understand it by visualization, online campaigns, create videos and on radio programs across the state” (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14).

In essence, OGD has sparked advocacy for more open government especially in local communities, these CSOs have used this data to engage people in local communities, build trust, and ownership for any project which the government earmarks in their budget documents till it is accomplished (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14). For instance, the quest for OGD has sparked advocacy initiatives such as Follow The Money, Tracka (www.tracka.ng), www.govspend.ng, www.openstates.ng, www.me.budgit.org, etc.

4.2.8 Missing data

Data completeness is one of the tenets of data quality. Missing data are not a new phenomenon in Nigeria’s OGD journey (Ojekunle, 2021). When interviewees were

quizzed on missing data, they mentioned that there are occasional missing data and data completeness cases.

One respondent said: “Yes, it happens, especially for FAAC. Sometimes, it does not come out early, and other times, they mistakenly give us the information that they have given us before. But we always call their attention to these things and sometimes, they even call our own attention to it” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22).

Another respondent stated that, “Data are not usually complete. They do not give the full details of what is going on in the budget document. Budgeting, release, and implementation are three different things. Some things might be budgeted for, but release has not happened, and they are evasive when you ask for full details” (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14). However, “some data are nonexistent in the first place. You cannot even find them when you comb through government database (Interviewee 1, personal communication, August 4). In the case of Nigeria, some social statistics data are missing such as full figures of election outcomes before 2011, land ownership and property data, and so on.

4.2.9 FOI

The FOI act was signed in 2011 and it has become instrumental for individuals and organizations seeking information from public MDAs. Mejabi et al. (2017) study has established a strong intersection between open data and the FOI act, that they are complementary rather than competing. When interviewees were quizzed about MDAs responsiveness to FOIs for data and information, one of them stated that:

“They are always very responsive to us. I mean, save some that are very stubborn. But when you see BudgIT requesting for something, you know that you might be in trouble if you do not respond. So, I think MDA response to FOI request depends on how much clout you have built as an organization and as a person” (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22).

Also, another interviewee had a contrary response on FOI:

A lot of the time they do not respond to FOI request. I just got a response from the office of secretary to the government of the federation, where we

requested for information on the amount earmarked for the controversial Nigeria Air, the response we got is they are not obliged to give us this state data and transferred us to other federal ministries. We have sent a similar FOI request letter to these ministries, and we are yet to get any further information” (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14).

There are well-documented cases and instances of Nigerian government not responding to FOI requests and which calls into questions the government’s accountability and transparency policy (Ojekunle, 2021; Adah, 2023). Also, Ezema (2023) analysis of government websites revealed that while some have information on FOI, most of them do not have a FOI portal. The fact FOI is not domesticated in several states across the country contributes to the challenge of requesting data and information from state governments.

4.2.10 Open data challenges

Open data in Nigeria has existential and developing challenges. When interviewees were questioned on challenges they encounter with open data in Nigeria, the challenges they listed includes data not being in machine readable formats, data not being up-to-date or outdated data, lateness in publishing data, data incompleteness, lack of trust in government data, issues around FOI domestication, lack of skilled technical personnel, corruption, and political will. The challenges highlighted by interviewee corroborates the findings of Ezema’s (2019) study on the status and challenges of OGD in Nigeria.

4.3 Summary of findings

The study’s findings provide analytical responses to the research questions. On improvement in the availability and accessibility of open data in Nigeria since 2017, the interface analysis of OGD portals revealed that more portals have been created since Nigeria joined OGP and from respondents’ perspectives, data visualization is improving but requires more input to create a better understanding of OGD. However, the unresponsiveness to requests for FOIs is limiting OGD availability and access in Nigeria.

Then, open data portals in Nigeria are promoting fiscal transparency through the creating of the open treasury portal and NOCOPO.

Open Treasury portal started from advocacy and campaigns to understand how the government is spending our money. Then, you have platforms like open treasury that tell you how much the government has moved to MDAs with the details of what those monies are used for. Also, the last dataset we got from the open treasury portal, payments without descriptions have reduced drastically. The last analysis of the portal that we did, we had to call them out on a lot of payments without descriptions. Between January to June 2023, our analysis shows that just six payments were without description from that six-month period (Interviewee 3, personal communication, August 22).

The institutional transparency outcomes from open data portals in Nigeria is becoming more obvious daily, for instance, the NBS has a data calendar for its releases, and only postponed if that date falls on a weekend (NBS Nigeria, 2023). However, the FOI act has made it easier to hold government accountable to be transparent and accountable with CSO doing online and offline advocacy for more open data.

We have encountered a lot of issues around incomplete data, and when we send FOI letters, if there is no response, we resort to online advocacy. One time, we put up information on our social media page saying this state government has received a particular amount of money which we know is not accurate. Swiftly, the state government replied to the post saying we did not receive that amount of money, and this is the exact amount we have received from the government. This created an online conversation on government being open about their operations (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14).

There are recurring challenges and barriers to implementing open data for good governance in Nigeria such as lack of availability and access to data, delay in data publishing, data incompleteness, lack of appropriate data visualization, issues around FOI domestication, lack of skilled technical personnel, corruption, and political will.

4.4 Limitations of the research

During the study, one of the limitations of the research is the inability to interview federal civil servants of the Ministry of Finance, Budget and National Planning. This is despite

sending mails and submitting physical letters which were received and acknowledged. This could be blamed on the change in government and appointment of new ministers in the country. However, this could have been averted if MDAs were more open to granting FOI requests.

Another limitation is the positionality of the interviewees and some of their responses to the questions posed to them which could be biased to promote their own predetermined narratives due to the purpose for the interview. However, the major limitation of this study is inability to conduct in-person qualitative research due to time constraints and geographical limitations. The interviews were conducted virtually and there was not enough time to pursue leads and contacts that would get me physical interviews at the ministry.

4.5 Implications for policy

The state of open data in Nigeria is still taking shape but it has had positive impact on development practices. One of the things that stood out in my interview with CSOs was how the project monitoring that stated through open data led to more social good for one community, “if you go to the community now, it has a computer center and primary school which were not there before the advocacy campaign started” (Interviewee 2, personal communication, August 14). The two CSOs also talked about partnering with the government to train staff on capacity development.

The implication of this study shows how government should encourage more partnership with CSOs to improve their open data portals and make data more available and in a timely fashion. This partnership could also help them build trust with citizens and improve their data quality and access.

5.0 CONCLUSION

OGD portals in Nigeria has become an instrument for monitoring and measuring development impact. This is one of the conclusions drawn from the comprehensive analysis of government websites and portals and how they influence data accessibility, availability, and completeness. Through systematic textual analysis and interviews with key stakeholders, this study has also explored the broader implications of open data within the Nigerian context and its impact on development practices.

To start with, it is essential to acknowledge the impact of OGD portals such as NOCOPO, open treasury portal, NBS and BOF website on improving transparency within the Nigerian government. These portals have become instrumental in disseminating critical information about government expenditures, procurement activities, and budget performance. By offering unprecedented access to financial and operational data, these platforms have played a pivotal role in increasing transparency across government operations.

Moving beyond transparency, open data initiatives have significantly enhanced accountability in Nigeria's public space. CSOs have harnessed open data to scrutinize government projects, track budget allocations, and hold public officials accountable for their actions. This has led to the emergence of data-driven advocacy campaigns, such as Follow The Money and Tracka, which place substantial pressure on government agencies and public office holders to ensure fiscal responsibility and transparency. CSOs have also used open data to engage with local communities and charge them to take ownership of development projects coming to their communities by monitoring and asking questions.

Nevertheless, a meticulous analysis of these portals' interfaces has unearthed diverse levels of user-friendliness and data visualization. While certain portals exhibit rich data visualization and accessibility features, others fall short in these aspects. Notably, the NOCOPO interface was found wanting in terms of accessibility and user-friendliness.

Through this study, challenges in data accessibility were identified, including the absence of a central repository for government data and issues with data formats. Data availability was also a concern, with delays in data publication and occasional missing data reported. Despite improvements in data availability, there is still room for enhancement. In the realm of data protection and privacy, the Data Protection Act, 2023 signifies Nigeria's

commitment to international data protection standards. This is a crucial step for maintaining public trust in open data initiatives as well as ensuring data security and privacy.

However, challenges persist in the Nigerian OGD landscape, including incomplete data, delays in data publication, and concerns related to FOI responsiveness. Addressing these challenges is imperative to fully harness open data potential in advancing transparency, accountability, and good governance in Nigeria.

5.1 Recommendations

Taking into perspective the literature review, data collection, analysis and findings from this study gives room to give some recommendation that would improve data completeness. However, interviewees opined that the government has the responsibility to continue re-training their staff to improve capacity development. Another point of agreement is that the Nigeria MDAs partnering with CSOs to conduct research and impact analysis studies on the data they put out will give them feedback to help improve their process and data collection, analysis, visualization, and publication processes.

A critical recommendation arising from this study underscores the absence of a centralized repository for crucial social statistics like population, poverty, and health outcomes data within the government. Establishing such a central data pool in Nigeria, coupled with ongoing data collection efforts, is essential. This approach would effectively address data gaps, ensuring comprehensive information availability for data-driven policymaking. Recent debates surrounding resource distribution based on population (the subsidy palliatives) highlight the urgency of this issue. Without up-to-date data, decisions risk being skewed. Continuous nationwide data collection and meticulous maintenance of birth and death registers would mitigate these challenges, supporting more equitable policy formulation and allocation.

More importantly, continuity of government requires legal backing. The change in administration or political appointee in MDAs would have minimal effect on data availability and access, if there is a policy document or an act in place to ensure continuity in OGD, sending out information and data.

5.2 Inferences and further study

This study contributes constructive and evidence-backed insights to the academic discourse of open data within the context of development practices, especially in Nigeria. It infers that OGD has notably improved transparency by providing access to critical government financial information and CSOs leverage this data to hold public officials accountable.

For policy practice, this study highlights the pivotal role of OGD portals in improving transparency, accountability, and data completeness within the Nigerian government. The findings underscore the need for enhancing the user-friendliness and accessibility of OGD platforms while emphasizing the importance of government-CSOs collaboration, continuous data collection and a central data repository.

To further advance open data initiatives in Nigeria, future research should explore establishing a central data repository, implementing continuous data collection mechanisms, creating a legal framework for data continuity, assessing capacity development programs, and examining government-CSO collaborations. These studies will shed light on open data impact on transparency, accountability, and good governance in the country.

Bibliography

- Adah, G., 2023. SERAP: Government Lacks Transparency, Only 10% of FOI Requests Are Responded To. *Arise News*. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.arise.tv/serap-government-lacks-transparency-only-10-of-foi-requests-are-responded-to/> [accessed: 08 September 2023].
- Agba, J. U., Ogri, E. U., and Adomi, K. O., 2018. The Nigerian Freedom of Information (FOI) Act and the Right to Know: Bridging the Gap between Principle and Practice, *New Media and Mass Communication*, 73, pp. 21-31.
- Araujo, J. F. F. E. d., and Tejedo-Romero, F., 2016. Local government transparency index: Determinants of municipalities' rankings. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 29(4), 327–347.
- Australian Government Productivity Commission, 2023. *5-year Productivity Inquiry: Australia's data and digital dividend*, Vol. 4, Inquiry Report no. 100. Canberra, Australia: Commonwealth of Australia.
- Bannister, F., and Connolly, R., 2011. The Trouble with Transparency: A Critical Review of Openness in e-Government. *Policy and Internet*, 3(1):8, pp. 1-30.
- Bvuma, S. and Joseph, B. K., 2019. Empowering Communities and Improving Public Services Through Open Data: South African Local Government Perspective. In: M. P. Rodríguez Bolívar, K. J. Bwalya, and C. G. Reddick (eds), *Governance Models for Creating Public Value in Open Data Initiatives*. Public Administration and Information Technology, 31, pp. 141-160. Springer.
- Charalabidis, Y., Zuiderwijk, A., Alexopoulos, C., Janssen, M., Lampoltshammer, T., and Ferro, E., 2018. *The World of Open Data: Concepts, Methods, Tools and Experiences*. Germany: Springer International Publishing.
- Crawford, G., and Abdulai, A.-G., 2009. The World Bank and Ghana's Poverty Reduction Strategies: Strengthening the State or Consolidating Neoliberalism? *Labour, Capital and Society / Travail, Capital et Société*, 42(1/2), pp. 82–115.
- Daily Trust, 2022. FG Restores Open Treasury Portal, Financial Records Of Presidency, Army, Navy, MDAs Missing. *Daily Trust*. [Online]. Available at:

<https://dailytrust.com/fg-restores-open-treasury-portal-financial-records-of-presidency-navy-mdas-missing/> [accessed: 05 September 2023].

Davies, T., Walker, S., Rubinstein, M., and Perini, F. (eds.), 2019. *The State of Open Data: Histories and Horizons*. Cape Town and Ottawa: African Minds and International Development Research Centre.

Ezema, I. J., 2019. Status and Challenges of Open Government Data in Nigeria: An Informetric Analysis of Websites of Government Ministries and Organizations. *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Scientometrics and Informetrics (ISSI2021) in Leuven, Belgium, 12–15 July 2021*, pp. 375 – 386. Leuven, Belgium: Katholieke Universiteit.

Ezema, I. J., 2023. Availability and Access to Government Research Data and Freedom of Information in Nigeria: An Evaluation of Selected Government Websites. *88th International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) World Library and Information Congress (WLIC) Report, 2023 Rotterdam*. Available at: <https://repository.ifla.org/handle/123456789/2786> [accessed: 08 September 2023].

Ganapati, S., Cid, G. P., and Reddick, C. G., 2019. Online Fiscal Transparency of US State Governments: An Analysis Using Public Value Framework. In M. P. Rodríguez Bolívar, K. J. Bwalya, and C. G. Reddick (eds.), *Governance Models for Creating Public Value in Open Data Initiatives*, pp. 55-84. Germany: Springer International Publishing.

Goldstein, B., Dyson, L., and Nemani, A., 2013. *Beyond Transparency: Open Data and the Future of Civic Innovation*. United States: Code for America Press.

Government of Canada, 2022. *Canada National Action Plan on Open Government 2022-24*. Ottawa, Canada: Government of Canada.

Gray, J. W. Y., 2023. What do data portals do? Tracing the politics of online devices for making data public. *Data and Policy*, 5(10), pp. 1-27.

Gurin, J., 2014. Open Governments, Open Data: A New Lever for Transparency, Citizen Engagement, and Economic Growth. *SAIS Review of International Affairs*, 34(1): 71-82.

Iwasaki, N. and Obi, T., 2015. *A Decade of World E-Government Rankings*. Netherlands: IOS Press.

- Kariuki, P., Adeleke, J. A., and Ofusori, L. O., 2019. The role of open data in enabling fiscal transparency and accountability in municipalities in Africa: South Africa and Nigeria case studies. In *Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance (ICEGOV 2020)*, 23-25 September 2020, Athens, Greece. pp. 410-418.
- Kim, H., 2018. Interlinking Open Government Data in Korea using Administrative District Knowledge Graph. *Journal of Information Science Theory and Practice*, 6, pp. 18-30.
- Kitchin, R., 2014. *The Data Revolution: Big Data, Open Data, Data Infrastructures and Their Consequences*. California, U.S.A: Sage Publications Inc.
- Manovich, L., 2008. Data visualization as new abstraction and as anti-sublime. In B. Hawk, D.M. Rieder, and O. Oviedo (eds.), *Small Tech: The Culture of Digital Tools*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.
- Manyika, J., Chui, M., Farrell, D., Van Kuiken, S., Groves, P., and Doshi, E. A., 2013. *Open data: Unlocking innovation and performance with liquid information*. London, England: McKinsey Global Institute.
- Mayernik, M. S., 2017. Open data: Accountability and transparency. *Big Data and Society*, 4(2), pp. 1-5.
- Mejabi, O. V., Azeez, A. L., Adedoyin, A., and Oloyede, M. O., 2014. Case Study Report on Investigation of the Use of the Online National Budget of Nigeria.
- Mejabi, O. V., Azeez, A. L., Adedoyin, A., and Oloyede, M. O., 2017. Intersection of Open Data and Freedom of Information Practice in Nigeria. *Journal of Information Science Theory and Practice*, 9(1), pp. 31-51.
- Mkandawire, T., 2010. Aid, Accountability, and Democracy in Africa. *Social Research*, 77(4), pp. 1149–1182.
- Moore, S., 2018. Towards a Sociology of Institutional Transparency: Openness, Deception and the Problem of Public Trust. *Sociology*, 52(2), pp. 416–430.
- Mutuku, L. and Tinto, T. I., 2019. Open data around the world: Sub-Saharan Africa. In T. Davies, S. Walker, M. Rubinstein, & F. Perini (eds.), *The state of open data: Histories*

and Horizons, pp. 549–564. Cape Town and Ottawa: African Minds and International Development Research Centre.

Nayek, J. K. R., 2018. Evaluation of Open Data Government Sites: A Comparative Study. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*, 1781. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/188128707.pdf> [accessed: 07 September 2023].

NBS Nigeria., 2023 [X] 13 March. Available at: https://twitter.com/NBS_Nigeria/status/1635303950294601730 [accessed: 08 September 2023].

NDPC, 2023. *Nigeria Data Protection Commission Website*. [Online]. Available at: <https://ndpc.gov.ng/Home/about> [accessed: 05 September 2023].

Neurath, M., and Kinross, R., 2009. *The Transformer: Principles of Making Isotype Charts*. London, United Kingdom: Hyphen Press.

OECD, 2014. *Data-driven innovation for growth and well-being: Interim synthesis report*. Paris, France: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development.

OECD, 2018. *Open Government Data in Mexico: The Way Forward*. Paris, France: OECD Digital Government Studies, OECD Publishing.

OECD, 2019a. *Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data: Reconciling Risks and Benefits for Data Re-use Across Societies*. France: OECD Publishing.

OECD, 2019b. *OECD Economic Surveys: New Zealand*. Paris, France: OECD Digital Government Studies, OECD Publishing.

OECD, 2019c. *OECD Economic Surveys: China*. Paris, France: OECD Digital Government Studies, OECD Publishing.

OECD, 2019d. *Government at a Glance Southeast Asia 2019*. Paris, France: OECD Digital Government Studies, OECD Publishing.

OGP, 2017. *Nigeria National Action Plan 2017-2019*. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.opengovpartnership.org/documents/nigeria-national-action-plan-2017-2019/> [accessed: 04 September 2023].

OGP, 2022. *Ghana Action Plan Review 2021-2023. OGP Independent Reporting Mechanism*. [Online]. Available at:

<https://www.opengovpartnership.org/documents/ghana-action-plan-review-2021-2023/>
[accessed: 24 June 2023].

OGP, 2023. Open Contracting (NG0002). *Open Government Partnerships*. [Online]. Available at:

https://www.opengovpartnership.org/members/nigeria/commitments/NG0002/#_ednref26
[accessed: 05 September 2023].

Ojekunle, A., 2021. Missing documents, deleted data, how inefficiency characterised Nigeria's Open Treasury Portal. *Dataphyte*. [Online]. Available at:
<https://www.dataphyte.com/latest-reports/development/missing-documents-deleted-data-how-inefficiency-characterised-nigerias-open-treasury-portal/> [accessed: 08 September 2023].

Olawoyin, O., 2020. Nigeria's open treasury portal defective, needs review – BudgIT. *Premium Times*. [Online]. Available at:

<https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/top-news/396130-nigerias-open-treasury-portal-defective-needs-review-budgit.html> [accessed: 05 September 2023].

Premium Times, 2023. Tinubu signs data protection bill into law. *Premium Times*. [Online]. Available at:

<https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/more-news/604442-tinubu-signs-data-protection-bill-into-law.html> [accessed: 08 September 2023].

Reno-Weber, T., and Niblock, B., 2013. Beyond Transparency: Louisville's Strategic Use of Data to Drive Continuous Improvement. In B. Goldstein, L. Dyson, and A. Nemani, (eds.), *Beyond Transparency: Open Data and the Future of Civic Innovation*, pp. 211-232. United States: Code for America Press.

Ricker, B., Cinnamon, J. and Dierwechter, Y., 2020. When open data and data activism meet: An analysis of civic participation in Cape Town, South Africa. *The Canadian Geographer*, 64 (3), pp. 360-373.

Rodríguez Bolívar, M. P., Bwalya, K. J. and Reddick, C. G. (eds.), 2019. *Governance Models for Creating Public Value in Open Data Initiatives*. Germany: Springer International Publishing.

Sahara Reporters, 2018. Bureau Of Public Procurement To Create Portal For Monitoring Govt's Contracts. *Sahara Reporters*. [Online]. Available at: <https://saharareporters.com/2018/04/20/bureau-public-procurement-create-portal-monitoring-govts-contracts> [accessed: 05 September 2023].

Saxena, S. and Muhammad, I., 2018. The impact of open government data on accountability and transparency. *Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, 34(3), pp. 204-216.

Smith, M. L. and Seward, R. K., 2020. *Making Open Development Inclusive: Lessons from IDRC Research*. United States: MIT Press.

Stagars, M., 2016. *Open Data in Southeast Asia: Towards Economic Prosperity, Government Transparency, and Citizen Participation in the ASEAN*. Germany: Springer International Publishing.

The Punch, 2019. Buhari inaugurates treasury portal, says Nigerians can now monitor govt spending. *The Punch Nigeria*. [Online]. Available at: <https://punchng.com/buhari-inaugurates-open-treasury-portal-says-nigerians-can-now-monitor-govt-spending/> [accessed: 05 September 2023].

Tunji, B., 2023. Data breaches: FG threatens to prosecute MDAs CEOs. *The Punch*. [Online]. Available at: <https://punchng.com/data-breaches-fg-threatens-to-prosecute-mdas-ceos/> [accessed: 08 September 2023].

Udegbonam, O. and Igwe, U., 2022. Major glitch takes down multiple Nigerian govt websites. *Premium Times*. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/510420-major-glitch-takes-down-multiple-nigerian-govt-websites.html> [accessed: 05 September 2023].

UNDP, 2022. *United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Digital Strategy 2022 – 2025*. New York, U.S.A: UNDP.

UNESCO, 2020. From Promise to Practice: Access to Information for Sustainable Development. *2020 UNESCO Report on the Monitoring and Reporting of SDG Indicator 16.10.2 (Public Access to Information)*. UNESCO Publishing.

- Van Loenen, B., 2018. The Development of Open Data in The Netherlands. In B. van Loenen, G. Vancauwenberghe, and J. Cromptvoets (eds.), *Open Data Exposed*, pp. 215-232. Germany: Springer.
- Van Loenen, B., Vancauwenberghe, G., and Cromptvoets, J. (eds.), 2018. *Open Data Exposed*. Germany: Springer.
- Van Schalkwyk, F., Verhulst, S. G., Magalhaes, G., Pane, J., and Walker, J., 2017. *The Social Dynamics of Open Data*. United Kingdom: African Minds.
- Vancauwenberghe, G. and Fawcett, J., 2018. Open Data in the United Kingdom. In B. van Loenen, G. Vancauwenberghe, and J. Cromptvoets (eds.), *Open Data Exposed*, pp. 195-214. Germany: Springer.
- Wang, V., and Shepherd, D., 2020. Exploring the extent of openness of open government data – A critique of open government datasets in the UK. *Government Information Quarterly*, 37, pp. 1-10.
- World Bank, 2015. Open data for Sustainable development: Transport and ICT. *World Bank Policy Note ICT01*. Washington DC, U.S.A: World Bank Group.
- Zanmiller, A., 2015. The State of Open Data in American Local Governments. [Online]. Available at: <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/32421221.pdf> [accessed: 24 June 2023].
- Zuiderwijk, A., Loukis, E., Alexopoulos, C., Janssen, M., and Jeffery, K., 2014. Elements for the development of an open data marketplace. In *Conference for e-democracy and open government (CeDEM14)*, p. 309-322.

OGD Websites

- BOF, 2023. *Budget Office of the Federation Website*. [Online]. Available at: <https://budgetoffice.gov.ng/> [accessed: 05 September2023].
- NBS, 2023. *National Bureau of Statistics Website*. [Online]. Available at: <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng/> [accessed: 05 September2023].
- NOCOPO, 2023. *Nigeria Open Contracting Portal (NOCOPO) Website*. [Online]. Available at: <http://nocopo.bpp.gov.ng/> [accessed: 05 September2023].

Open Treasury, 2023. *Open Treasury Portal*. [Online]. Available at:
<https://opentreasury.gov.ng/> [accessed: 05 September2023].

Appendix 1

List of interviewees

Interviewees	Organization	Rank/Position	Date of interview	Interview medium
Interviewee 1	Ominira Initiative for Economic Advancement	Executive Director	August 4, 2023	Microsoft Teams
Interviewee 2	Connected Development (CODE)	Community Engagement Manager	August 14, 2023	Microsoft Teams
Interviewee 3	BudgIT	Assistant Manager, International Growth	August 22, 2023	Microsoft Teams

Appendix 2

Ethical approval form

University of East Anglia
Norwich Research Park
Norwich, NR4 7TJ

Email: ethicsmonitor@uea.ac.uk
Web: www.uea.ac.uk

Study title: How Open Data is Reshaping Development Practices in Nigeria

Application ID: ETH2223-2053

Dear Muideen,

Your application was considered on 9th June 2023 by the DEV S-REC (School of International Development Research Ethics Subcommittee).

The decision is: **approved**.

You are therefore able to start your project subject to any other necessary approvals being given.

This approval will expire on **15th September 2023**.

Please note that your project is granted ethics approval only for the length of time identified above. Any extension to a project must obtain ethics approval by the DEV S-REC (School of International Development Research Ethics Subcommittee) before continuing.

It is a requirement of this ethics approval that you should report any adverse events which occur during your project to the DEV S-REC (School of International Development Research Ethics Subcommittee) as soon as possible. An adverse event is one which was not anticipated in the research design, and which could potentially cause risk or harm to the participants or the researcher, or which reveals potential risks in the treatment under evaluation. For research involving animals, it may be the unintended death of an animal after trapping or carrying out a procedure.

Any amendments to your submitted project in terms of design, sample, data collection, focus etc. should be notified to the DEV S-REC (School of International Development Research Ethics Subcommittee) in advance to ensure ethical compliance. If the amendments are substantial a new application may be required.

Approval by the DEV S-REC (School of International Development Research Ethics Subcommittee) should not be taken as evidence that your study is compliant with the UK General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR) and the Data Protection Act 2018. If you need guidance on how to make your study UK GDPR compliant, please contact the UEA Data Protection Officer (dataprotection@uea.ac.uk).

I would like to wish you every success with your project.

On behalf of the DEV S-REC (School of International Development Research Ethics Subcommittee)

Yours sincerely,

Ben Jones